

Influence of Ba[Mg₂Al₂N₄]Eu²⁺ phosphor particle size on optical properties of the 6000K CPW-LEDs

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we consider the red phosphor Ba[Mg₂Al₂N₄]Eu²⁺ as the novel recommendation for improving the optical properties of the 6000K conformal packaging WLEDs (CPW-LEDs). For this purpose, we investigate the influence of the Ba[Mg₂Al₂N₄]Eu²⁺ particle size on the optical properties in terms of CCT, CQS, CRI, and LO using the Light Tools and Mat Lab software. From the research results, it can be observed that the optical properties of the 6000K CPW-LEDs are significantly influenced by the size of the Ba[Mg₂Al₂N₄]Eu²⁺ particle. The CRI and CQS increase from 65 to 67 and 64 to 68 while the size of the Ba[Mg₂Al₂N₄]Eu²⁺ particle varies from 1 μm to 10 μm, respectively. This research can provide a novel recommendation for LEDs industry at this time.

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1. INTRODUCTION

With the excellent characters such as lifetime, efficiency, and reliability, the light-emitting diodes (LEDs) is the main lighting generation in our time in the comparison with the conventional lighting methods with the huge disadvantages due to the significant energy losses based on high temperatures performance and massive Stokes shifts [1-10]. In the LEDs industry, the white light from the LEDs can be conducted in three ways. Firstly, the white light is generated by mixing blue, green, and red colors LEDs. In a second way, the white light can be conducted by adding the blue, green, and red phosphors in the phosphor layer LEDs. The last way, the white light can be generated by combining ultraviolet (UV) LEDs with blue, green, and red phosphors [11-20]. Commonly, the second way is the best way to conduct the white LEDs in the civil and industrial areas.

In this paper, the red phosphor Ba[Mg₂Al₂N₄]Eu²⁺ is considered as the modern solution for improving the optical properties of the 6000K conformal packaging WLEDs (CPW-LEDs). For this purpose, the influence of the Ba[Mg₂Al₂N₄]Eu²⁺ size on the optical properties in terms of CCT, CQS, CRI and LO is proposed and investigated using the Light Tools and Mat Lab software. From the research results, we can see that the optical properties of the 6000K CPW-LEDs is significantly influenced by the size of

the $\text{Ba}[\text{Mg}_2\text{Al}_2\text{N}_4]\text{Eu}^{2+}$ particle. The CRI and CQS increase from 65 to 67 and 64 to 68 while the size of the $\text{Ba}[\text{Mg}_2\text{Al}_2\text{N}_4]\text{Eu}^{2+}$ particle varies from 1 μm to 10 μm , respectively. Here are the main point of this research:

- Light Tools conduct the physical model of the 6000K CPW-LEDs.
- The scattering processes of CPW-LEDs phosphor layer is investigated by Mat Lab.
- The effect of the $\text{Ba}[\text{Mg}_2\text{Al}_2\text{N}_4]\text{Eu}^{2+}$ size on the D-CCT, CRI, CQS, and LO are investigated and convinced.

The rest of our paper can be proposed in the following sections. The second section provides the physical model, scattering processes of the 6000 K CPW-LEDs. The third section gives results and some discussions. The last section concludes this manuscript.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. The CPW-LEDs physical model

In this section, the real WLEDs is shown in Figure 1 (a). As previous researches [13-15] the 6600K CPW-LEDs is simulated by Light Tool software with the primary parameters as:

- We set the depth as 2.07 mm, the inner and outer radius of the reflector as 8 mm and 9.85 mm, respectively.
- LED chips are covered with a fixed thickness of 0.08 mm and 2.07 mm. Each blue chip has a dimension of 1.14 mm by 0.15 mm, the radiant flux of 1.16 W Figure 1 (b) [15-19].

Figure 1. (a) The real WLEDs, (b) The physical model

2.2. The scattering processes in the phosphor compounding

For investigating the influence of the size of the $\text{Ba}[\text{Mg}_2\text{Al}_2\text{N}_4]\text{Eu}^{2+}$ particle on the optical properties of the 6000K CPW-LEDs, the scattering processes in the phosphor layer of the CPW-LEDs is formulated by using Mie Theory as in [20-25]. The scattering coefficient is formulated as;

$$\mu_{sca}(\lambda) = \int N(r)C_{sca}(\lambda, r)dr \quad (1)$$

the reduced scattering coefficient is defined as;

$$g(\lambda) = 2\pi \int_{-1}^1 p(\theta, \lambda, r)f(r) \cos \theta d \cos \theta dr \quad (2)$$

The influence of the $\text{Ba}[\text{Mg}_2\text{Al}_2\text{N}_4]\text{Eu}^{2+}$ particle size on the scattering process in the phosphor compounding is investigating using Math Lab software. As shown in Figure 2, the scattering coefficient (SC) increases significantly while the size of the $\text{Ba}[\text{Mg}_2\text{Al}_2\text{N}_4]\text{Eu}^{2+}$ particle varies from 1 μm to 10 μm . We can see that the SC with wavelength 555 nm is the highest values, and with wavelength 680 nm is the lowest values. Furthermore, the effect of the $\text{Ba}[\text{Mg}_2\text{Al}_2\text{N}_4]\text{Eu}^{2+}$ particle size on the reduced scattering coefficient (RSC) is plotted in Figure 4 with varying the red phosphor size from 1 μm to 10 μm . As shown in Figure 3, the RSC with the wavelengths 453, 555, 680 nm have the same massive increase in connection with the rising of the $\text{Ba}[\text{Mg}_2\text{Al}_2\text{N}_4]\text{Eu}^{2+}$ size from 1 μm to 10 μm . It can be observed that the size of the $\text{Ba}[\text{Mg}_2\text{Al}_2\text{N}_4]\text{Eu}^{2+}$ particle has a massive impact on the SC in the phosphor layer.

Figure 2. Scattering coefficient (SC)

Figure 3. Reduced scattering coefficient (RSC)

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the influence of the Ba[Mg₂Al₂N₄]Eu²⁺ particle size on the optical properties in terms of D-CCT, CRI, CQS and LO is investigated and discussed by using the Light Tool software. As shown in Figure 4, the D-CCT has a slight increase when we vary the size of the Ba[Mg₂Al₂N₄]Eu²⁺ phosphor from 1 μm to 10 μm. In Figure 4, the D-CCT increase from 1200K to 1500K with rising the Ba[Mg₂Al₂N₄]Eu²⁺ size. Furthermore, the influence of the Ba[Mg₂Al₂N₄]Eu²⁺ size on the CQS is illustrated in Figure 5. We can see that CQS rises significantly while the size of Ba[Mg₂Al₂N₄]Eu²⁺ phosphor rises from 1 to 5 μm, then keep the same values with size from 6 to 10 μm. In the same way, the CRI has a huge increase, and after that has a slight increase when the size of the Ba[Mg₂Al₂N₄]Eu²⁺ up to 10 μm as plotted in Figure 6. Finally, the LO versus the size of the Ba[Mg₂Al₂N₄]Eu²⁺ phosphor is showed in Figure 7. The LO has a huge decrease and then keep the same values after that. From the research results, it can be observed that the size of the Ba[Mg₂Al₂N₄]Eu²⁺ particle has a huge impact on the optical properties of the 6000K CPW-LEDs.

Figure 4. The D-CCT

Figure 5. CQS

Figure 6. CRI

Figure 7. LO

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the red phosphor Ba[Mg₂Al₂N₄]Eu²⁺ is considered as the novel recommendation for improving the optical properties of the 6000K conformal packaging WLEDs (CPW-LEDs). For this purpose, the influence of the Ba[Mg₂Al₂N₄]Eu²⁺ size on the optical properties in terms of CCT, CQS, CRI and LO is proposed and investigated using the Light Tools and Mat Lab software. From the research results, we can see that the optical properties of the 6000K CPW-LEDs is significantly influenced by the size of the Ba[Mg₂Al₂N₄]Eu²⁺ particle. The CRI and CQS increase from 65 to 67 and 64 to 68 while the size of the Ba[Mg₂Al₂N₄]Eu²⁺ phosphor particle vary from 1 μm to 10 μm, respectively.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Sheng Liu, Xiaobing Luo, "Design of LED Packaging Applications," *LED Packaging for Lighting Applications*, pp. 215–315, July 2011.
- [2] Gibney, Elizabeth. 2014. "Nobel for Blue LED That Revolutionized Lighting," *Nature*, vol. 514, no. 7521, pp. 152–153, 9 October 2014.
- [3] Winkler, Holger, Quang Trinh, Peter Bodrogi, and Tran Quoc Khanh, "LED Lighting: Technology and Perception," Weinheim: Wiley-VCH, November 2014.
- [4] Luo, Xiaobing, Run Hu, Sheng Liu, and Kai Wang. 2016. "Heat and Fluid Flow in High-Power LED Packaging and Applications," *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science*, vol. 56, pp. 1–32, September 2016.
- [5] Hu, Run, Xiaobing Luo, and Sheng Liu. 2011. "Effect of the Amount of Phosphor Silicone Gel on Optical Property of White Light-Emitting Diodes Packaging," *2011 12th International Conference on Electronic Packaging Technology and High Density Packaging*, Shanghai, pp. 1-4, 2011.
- [6] Phu Tran Tin, N. H. K. Nhan, Minh Tran, T. T. Trang, Tan N. Nguyen and Miroslav Voznak, "Co-Doping Red-Emitting Sr₂SisN₈:Eu²⁺ Into Yellow-Emitting Phosphor-Packaging For Enhancing The Optical Properties Of The 8500 K Remote-Phosphor Packaging Wleds," *Digest Journal of Nanomaterials and Biostructures*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 1027-1034, October 2018.
- [7] Phu Tran Tin, N. H. K. Nhan, T. H. Q. Minh, Miroslav Voznak, Tan N. Nguyen and Tran Thanh Trang, "Sr₂SisN₈:Eu²⁺ phosphor: a novel recommendation for improving the lighting performance of the 7000K remote-packaging white LEDs," *Proceedings of The Estonian Academy of Sciences*, vol. 67, no. 4, pp. 337-341, 2018.
- [8] Sommer, Christian, Franz-Peter Wenzl, Paul Hartmann, Peter Pachler, Marko Schweighart, Stefan Tasch, and Günther Leising, "Tailoring of the Color Conversion Elements in Phosphor-Converted High-Power LEDs by Optical Simulations," *IEEE Photonics Technology Letters*, vol. 20, no. 9, pp. 739-741, May 1, 2008.
- [9] Li, Shuiming, Kai Wang, Fei Chen, Shuang Zhao, Zhili Zhao, and Sheng Liu, "Angular Color Uniformity Enhancement of Phosphor Converted White LEDs Integrated with Compact Modified Freeform TIR Components," *2012 13th International Conference on Electronic Packaging Technology & High-Density Packaging*, Guilin, pp. 1487-1490, 2012.
- [10] Zongyuan Liu, Sheng Liu, Kai Wang, and Xiaobing Luo, "Analysis of Factors Affecting Color Distribution of White LEDs," *2008 International Conference on Electronic Packaging Technology & High Density Packaging*, Shanghai, pp. 1-8, 2008.
- [11] Z. Liu, Sheng Liu, Kai Wang, and Xiaobing Luo, "Optical Analysis of Color Distribution in White LEDs With Various Packaging Methods," *IEEE Photonics Technology Letters*, vol. 20, no. 24, pp. 2027-2029, Dec 15, 2008.
- [12] Zongyuan Liu, Sheng Liu, Kai Wang, and Xiaobing Luo, "Effects of Phosphor's Location on LED Packaging Performance," *2008 International Conference on Electronic Packaging Technology & High Density Packaging*, Shanghai, pp. 1-7, 2008.
- [13] Minh, Tran Hoang Quang, Nguyen Huu Khanh Nhan, Nguyen Doan Quoc Anh, and Hsiao-Yi Lee, "Red-Emitting α-SrO•3B₂O₃:Sm²⁺ Phosphor: an Innovative Application for Increasing Color Quality and Luminous Flux of Remote Phosphor White LEDs," *Journal of the Chinese Institute of Engineers*, vol. 40, no. 4, pp. 1-5, April 2017.
- [14] Anh, Nguyen Doan Quoc, Hsiao-Yi Lee, Tran Thanh Phuong, Nguyen Huu Khanh Nhan, Tran Hoang Quang Minh, and Truong Huu Ly, "Y₂O₃:Eu³⁺ Phosphor: a Novel Solution for an Increase in Color Rendering Index of Multi-Chip White LED Packages," *Journal of the Chinese Institute of Engineers*, vol. 40, no. 3, 2017.
- [15] N. H. K. Nhan, T. H. Q. Minh, Tan N. Nguyen, Miroslav Voznak and V. V. Huynh, "Effect of The Green-Emitting CaF₂:Ce³⁺, Tb³⁺ Phosphor Particles' Size On Color Rendering Index and Color Quality Scale Of The In-Cup Packaging Multichip White LEDs," *Digest Journal of Nanomaterials and Biostructures*, vol. 13, no. 2, May 2018.
- [16] N. H. K. Nhan, T. H. Q. Minh, V. V. Huynh, Phuong T. Tran, Tan N. Nguyen and Miroslav Voznak, "Improving optical performance of multi-chip white LEDs by bi-layers remote-packaging phosphors," *Journal of Optoelectronics and Advanced Materials*, vol. 20, no. 3-4, pp. 93-97, 2018.

- [17] N. H. K. Nhan, T. H. Q. Minh, Tan N. Nguyen and Miroslav Voznak, "Bi-layers Red-emitting $\text{Sr}_2\text{Si}_5\text{N}_8$: Eu^{2+} Phosphor and Yellow-emitting YAG: Ce Phosphor: A New Approach for Improving the Color Rendering Index of the Remote Phosphor Packaging WLEDs," *Current Optics and Photonics*, vol. 1, no. 6, pp. 613-617, 2017.
- [18] N. H. K. Nhan, T. H. Q. Minh, Tan N. Nguyen and Miroslav Voznak, "Red-emitting $\text{Ca}_2\text{Si}_5\text{N}_8\text{Eu}^{2+}$ phosphor: a new recommendation for improving color uniformity and color quality scale of the conformal packaging multi-chip white leds," *Journal of Ovonic Research*, vol. 13, no. 6, pp. 325-331, November 2017.
- [19] N. H. K. Nhan, T. H. Q. Minh, Tan N. Nguyen and Miroslav Voznak, "Co-Doping Green-Emitting $\text{Ca}_2\text{Si}_5\text{N}_8$: Ce^{3+} , Tb^{3+} and Yellow Emitting Phosphor Particles for Improving the CCT Deviation and Luminous Efficacy of the In-cup Phosphor Packaging WLEDs," *Digest Journal of Nanomaterials and Biostructures*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 891-898, July-September 2017.
- [20] Yumi Fukuda, Aoi Okada, and Ariane Keiko Albessard, "Luminescence Properties of Eu^{2+} Doped Red-Emitting Sr-Containing Sialon Phosphor," *Applied Physics Express*, vol. 5, no. 6, 30 May 2012.
- [21] Michael Quinten, "Beyond Mie's Theory II - The Generalized Mie Theory," *Optical Properties of Nanoparticle Systems*, pp. 317-339, January 2011.
- [22] Frisvad, Jeppe Revall, Niels Jørgen Christensen, and Henrik Wann Jensen, "Predicting the Appearance of Materials Using Lorenz-Mie Theory," *The Mie Theory Springer Series in Optical Sciences*, vol. 169, pp. 101-133, June 2012.
- [23] Mackowski, Daniel, "The Extension of Mie Theory to Multiple Spheres," *The Mie Theory Springer Series in Optical Sciences*, vol. 169, pp. 223-256, June 2012.
- [24] Thomas Wriedt, "Mie Theory: A Review," *The Mie Theory Springer Series in Optical Sciences*, vol. 169, pp. 55-71, June 2012.
- [25] X. Luo, R. Hu, "Chip packaging: Encapsulation of nitride LEDs," *Nitride Semiconductor Light-Emitting Diodes (LEDs)*, pp. 491-528, 2018.